

STUDIES ON THE DIELECTRIC POLARISATION AND THE DIPOLE MOMENTS OF ENANTIOMERS

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Dielectric polarisations and dipole moments of *d*, *l* and *dl* forms of camphor borneol and menthol at different concentrations have been determined to adduce support for the Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry and to investigate the nature of linkage in *dl* compounds

B. K. Singh and collaborators (*Curr. Sci.*, 1933, 3, 420; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 2A, 378 *et seq*) have shown from the studies of the values of viscosity, density and refractive index for solutions of *d*, *l* and racemic forms that the values were identical up to certain concentrations only and that at higher concentrations though the values for *d* and *l* forms agreed, as is to be expected from the Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry, the values for the racemic forms were apparently higher than the corresponding values for the active enantiomers. It was thus concluded that at higher concentrations the racemic forms were present as equimolecular compound of enantiomers.

In view of the above it was thought instructive to investigate the total polarisations and dipole moments of the enantiomers at different concentrations to see if further support could be obtained for Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry and to investigate the nature of linkage present in the *dl* compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substances used in the present investigation were freshly prepared, specially purified, and their melting points and rotatory powers were determined before the measurements of dielectric constant were made on them. The determinations of the dielectric constant were carried out in specially purified and recrystallised benzene by the heterodyne beat apparatus. The apparatus consists of two high frequency oscillatory circuits the output from which are electrically mixed to produce the beat frequency, which is amplified and detected with head-phones and a magic eye detector. A brief sketch of the apparatus is shown in Fig. 1.

In this diagram the two upper left 6c5 triodes are connected as a Franklin oscillator, which is well known for its high frequency stability approaching that of a crystal oscillator. Similarly the two lower left 6c5 tubes make up another such oscillator. L_1C_1 and L_2C_2 are the oscillatory circuits, and out of these components, C_2 is a precision standard calibrated condenser. C_3 is the test condenser, which is connected in parallel with C_2 with short, stiff wires, and the capacity of the test condenser becomes measured by the adjustment of C_2 to get zero beat in each case. C_4 , C_5 , C_6 and C_7 are very small adjustable capacities of values about 2 to 3 $\mu\mu\text{F}$. The output from the two Franklin oscillators is filtered at L_3 and L_4 and then subjected to electronic mixing in the

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FIG. 1

The number of the two upper left triodes is 6c5. The one next to the extreme right (6E5) is to be read as 6E₅.

pentagrid converter, 6L7. The absence of pulling between the two circuits was shown by the fact that zero beat, once it was adjusted, would remain unaltered for hours together. In fact, it was found that after the circuit had been adjusted for zero beat and then turned off, when it was turned on again on the next day, the adjustment was still perfect. The plate of 6L7 is connected to the grid (3) of the magic eye detector (6E5) and by this means the conditions of zero beat can be tested both visually and aurally. Near about the position the fluorescent cone begins to flicker, and at the correct position the flicker disappears, and there is a perfect silence in phones. We found the apparatus, which was assembled in the laboratory, highly satisfactory and sensitive.

Table I records the dipole moments of these sets of compounds and Table II shows the total polarisations of these and those of the camphorquinone at different concentrations.

TABLE I

Melting point and dipole moments of the enantiomers at 20°-21°.

Subs.	M. p.	*Dip. mom. $\mu \times 10^{18}$.	Subs.	M. p.	*Dip. mom. $\mu \times 10^{18}$.	Subs.	M. p.	*Dip. mom. $\mu \times 10^{18}$.
<i>d</i> -Camphor	176°	2.90	<i>d</i> -Borneol	208°	1.6	<i>d</i> Menthol	39°	1.54
<i>l</i> -Camphor	178.5	2.905	<i>l</i> -Borneol	206	1.59	<i>l</i> -Menthol	43	1.54
<i>dl</i> -Camphor	179	2.91	<i>dl</i> -Borneol	210.5	1.59	<i>dl</i> -Menthol	34	1.55

* Expressed in Debye unit.

The experimental error in the determination of the dipole moments is of the order 0.05 to 1%.

TABLE II

Total polarisation values at different concentrations at 20°.

Substances,	Concentration (in g./100 c.c. of benzene).					
	1%.	2%.	5%.	10%.	12%.	14%.
<i>d</i> -Camphor	235	235	233	230	228	226
<i>l</i> - "	235	235	232.5	230	228.5	222
<i>dl</i> - "	235	235	232	228	226	223
<i>d</i> -Borneol	102	102	99	97	94	92
<i>l</i> - "	102	102	98.5	97	94	91.5
<i>dl</i> - "	102	102	97	95	91	89
<i>d</i> -Menthol	105	105	104	102	100	98
<i>l</i> - "	105	105	104	102	99.5	98
<i>dl</i> - "	105	105	102.5	99	96.5	93
<i>d</i> -Camphorquinone	540	538	534	528	524	520
<i>l</i> - "	540	537	534	527	524	520
<i>dl</i> - "	540	537	528	520	514	508

DISCUSSION

The magnitude of the polarisation depends on the electron charge density distribution and the effective radius of the molecule. The dipole moment determinations of the *d* and *l* forms show that the values of the stereoisomers agree closely with each other. This indicates that the electron charge distribution and radius in each of these stereoisomers would be identical and hence the total energy would be the same as postulated by the law of molecular dissymmetry.

The racemic forms bear the same dipole moment values as are possessed by the *d* and *l* forms, which shows that at the low concentrations at which the dipole moments are measured in order to eliminate the solvent effect, the racemic form behaves as if it were a mixture of *d* and *l* forms.

The total polarisation determinations of the *d*, *l* and *dl* forms show that at the same concentrations the values of the *d* and *l* forms agree closely, while those of *dl* forms always differ. The differences become more and more pronounced as the concentrations are increased. This fact shows that at low concentrations the racemic compound decomposes to give *d* and *l* forms. This is indicative of the presence of a weak bond in case there is a compound formation.

The authors acknowledge their thanks to Dr. B. K. Singh for supplying some of the compounds, and to Prof. Mahan Singh for facilities and assistance provided.